

The TSP - Triangular Sieve of Primes

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Abstract: In this study, we introduce the TSP – Triangular Sieve of Primes. In addition to sieving prime numbers from composite numbers, TSP shows us very clearly how it also separates and classifies composites into squares, prime number squares, and non-square composites.

Keywords: Sieve of prime numbers; highly composite numbers; factors; pair of complementary divisors; fundamental theorem of arithmetic.

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In the first formal logic class, the teacher asks the students: "Why do you need to study mathematics?"

One student looked at the other, and after a short silence one of them replied: "I don't know, professor. Why do I need to study mathematics?"

"My son, there is no rich person who doesn't know mathematics. But just because you study mathematics doesn't mean you will be a rich person."

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1 Introduction

For this and other studies, we first need to make some conventions and notations. The most complete and up-to-date set can be found at “C000000 Conventions, notations, abbreviations, glossary, and references”[8].

The idea of this triangular sieve of primes (TSP) is inspired by the red and blue diagonal lines that appear in the MID figure below that we find in the Divisor Trek[9].

Figure 1. C000721 The straight lines $x = \pm n * y \pm n^2$ covering [C000722 \(A056737\)](#) the smallest differences in red, and covering [C000724 \(A063655\)](#) the smallest sums in blue.

These diagonals also appear in several other frameworks that we will look at throughout the studies. These other studies were also sources of inspiration for TSP and vice-versa.

2 The Triangular Sieve of Prime Numbers (TSP) engine

We fundament the TSP operation on right triangle similarity geometry over the XY axis in the Cartesian XY plane.

See the picture:

Figure 2. C002251 The TSP operation.

In the figure above, there are 4 similar right triangles: $\triangle DEF$, $\triangle YVD$, $\triangle DWX$, and $\triangle YOX$. From these triangles we have:

$$\tan \alpha = \frac{\overline{DE}}{\overline{EF}} = \frac{\overline{YV}}{\overline{VD}} = \frac{\overline{DW}}{\overline{WX}} = \frac{\overline{YO}}{\overline{OX}}$$

We call the right triangle $\triangle DEF$ the reference triangle. We require integer $n > 0$ and the side opposite to point F with a fixed value $\overline{DE} = 1$.

We can write the following equalities:

$$\tan \alpha = \frac{1}{d} = \frac{h}{n} = \frac{n}{m} = \frac{n+h}{n+m} = \frac{Y}{X}$$

We base the core principle of operation on

$$d = \frac{n}{h} \Leftrightarrow n = hd \Leftrightarrow h = \frac{n}{d}$$

Then,

$$m = nd = hd^2 = \frac{n^2}{h}$$

$$Y = n + h = n + \frac{n}{d} = \frac{n(d+1)}{d}$$

$$X = n + m = n + nd = n(d+1) = d \cdot Y = hd(d+1) = hd^2 + hd = \text{quadratic}$$

To use the TSP, we will always make the d and n integer numbers: h will be an integer number if and only if d is the integer divisor of the integer n .

In this study, we will call the diagonal line joining the points $X = (n+m, 0)$ and $Y = (0, n+h)$ the "hypotenuse line". These are the lines that always will cross the corner D of the square OVDW of the side n integer.

We name this corner as point $D = (n, n)$. There is a distinct point $D = (n, n)$ for every n integer. All points $D = (n, n)$ in the XY plane lie on the yellow 45° diagonal $x = y$.

For any integer values of n and d , always m and $X = n + m$ will be integers.

This is not always true for h and $Y = n + h$. For h and Y , we need to figure out all the relations between n and d so that h and $Y = n + h$ are integers. This will only happen when d is an integer divisor of n . This is the core of the TSP operation.

2.1 The pair of complementary divisors d and h

Because of $h = \frac{n}{d}$, and we impose that n and d to be integers, then h will not always be an integer for any pair of integers n and d . Then our target is to find for each n integer, all h as an integer number.

Since d is a distance, it always must be greater than 0. If $d = 0$ there is no triangle, but only the square with side n .

For every $d > n$, then $0 < h < 1$ is not an integer number.

Thus, if we search for $h = \text{integer}$, we need $h \geq 1$. So, we restrict $d \leq n$.

Because d are the integer divisors of n , then its range is $1 \leq d \leq n$.

Because $h = \frac{n}{d}$, and $1 \leq d \leq n$, then also the range of h is $1 \leq h \leq n$.

3 The trivial divisors

3.1 The smallest trivial divisors $d = 1$

For any integer $n \geq 1$, if $d = 1$ trivial divisor, then $h = n$ is the other trivial divisor and $m = n$. So, $X = Y = 2n$, and $\alpha = 45^\circ$. This means that for any n , whenever $d = 1$, Y will be an integer.

This is true because any $n = \text{integer}$ is always divisible by 1:

$$h = \frac{n}{d} = \frac{n}{1} = n = \text{integer}$$

If we vary n and keep $d = 1$, we will get the figure below over the MHL:

Figure 3. C002252 The TSP formation of the red diagonal $x = y + 2$ of the trivial divisors $d = 1$.

For each integer n over the yellow 45° diagonal $x = y$, there is a trivial divisor $d = 1$ over the red 45° diagonal $x = y + 2$. For each n , the red 45° diagonal $x = y + 2$ represents the point $F = (n + d, n - 1)$. The distance between the yellow diagonal line of the integers n and the red diagonal of the divisors $d = 1$ is $\sqrt{2}$.

The red line crosses (or covers) all the trivial divisors $d = 1$ of each integer n over the yellow 45° diagonal $x = y$.

All points of the $MHL[x, y] = x \text{ mhl } y$, when viewed as divisors of n , take on the value $d = (x \text{ mhl } y) - 1$. This occurs in all cases. This is because of the offset that exists between the $x \text{ mhl } y = 1$ values caused by the 45° slope of the diagonal of the squares.

The red diagonal line $x = y + 2$ in the Modular Hyperbolic Lattice grid represent all $d = 1$ trivial divisors and lie on the points of value 2 in MHL.

Each pair n and $d = 1$ form the blue hypotenuse lines in Figure 3.

All blue hypotenuse lines are in the form of $x = -y + 2n$. They are all parallel with slope $-\frac{x}{y} = -45^\circ$. This is the largest slope (α) for each of the hypotenuse lines of the integers n . The distance between the two consecutive blue hypotenuse lines above is also $\sqrt{2}$.

3.2 The largest trivial divisors $d = n$

Now, when we set n and make $d = n$, then $h = 1$, and $m = n^2$ (square number). In that case, $Y = n + 1$, the integers in offset $f = -1$. And $X = n^2 + n = n(n + 1)$, oblong number in offset $f = -1$. This means that for any integer number n , whenever $d = n$, Y will be an integer. This is true because any $n = integer$ is always divisible by itself:

$$h = \frac{n}{d} = \frac{n}{n} = 1 = integer$$

If we vary n and keep $d = n$, we will get hypotenuse lines in blue as per the figure below:

Figure 4. C002253 The TSP formation of the red diagonal $x = 2y + 2$ of the trivial divisors $d = n$, for any n .

The blue hypotenuse lines are in the form of $x = -ny + (n^2 + n) = n(n + 1 - y)$.

For $x = 0, y = n + 1$ which are the integer numbers in offset $f = -1$. The set of hypotenuse lines for all trivial divisors $d = n$, i.e., $h = 1$, crosses the Y-axis at values of $Y = n + h = n + 1$.

For $y = 0, x = n^2 + n = n + m = X$ which are the oblong numbers in offset $f = -1$.

The intersection between two consecutive hypotenuse lines for $d = n$ occurs at the points:

$$P\left(-\left(\frac{y}{2}\right)^2 + \frac{y}{2}, 2y\right) \Leftrightarrow x = -\left(\frac{y}{2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{y}{2}\right) \Leftrightarrow 4x + y^2 - 2y = 0$$

Figure 5. C002254 The TSP parabola $4x = -y^2 + 2y = y(-y + 2)$ of the intersection points between the consecutive hypotenuse lines for $d = n$.

The parabola that tangents all hypotenuse lines occur at the points:

$$P\left(-\left(\frac{y}{2}\right)^2 + \frac{y}{2} - \frac{1}{4}, 2y - 1\right) \Leftrightarrow x = -\left(\frac{y}{2}\right)^2 + \frac{y}{2} - \frac{1}{4} \Leftrightarrow 4x + y^2 - 2y + 1 = 0$$

Figure 6. C002255 The TSP parabola $4x = -y^2 + 2y - 1$ of the tangent points with the hypotenuse lines.

Figure 7. C002256 The TSP parabolas alternation between tangent points and crossing points.

4 The two “trivial” diagonals

For each integer n , the diagonals hypotenuse lines with slope -1 : n have the highest slope. This happens for trivial divisors $d = n$ and $h = 1$. Trivial divisors $d = n$ form the red diagonal with the equation $x_{d=n} = 2y + 2$ in Figure 8.

Figure 8. [C000670](#) C002263 The TSP two “trivial” diagonals in red $x_{d=1} = y + 2$ and $x_{d=n} = 2y + 2$ delimit the range of the integer divisors from the lower trivial divisor $d = 1$ to the largest trivial divisor $d = n$.

The maximum hypotenuse slope for each n is at slope $-n:n - 45^\circ$ for $d = 1$ and $h = n$.

All trivial divisors of value $d = 1$ of all integers n on the yellow 45° diagonal form a line over the MHL. They form the red line with the equation $x_{d=1} = y + 2$ of the divisors $d = 1$

Because of the formation of the trivial red diagonal $x_{d=1} = y + 2$ for the divisors $d = 1$, any n in the Modular Hyperbolic Lattice in Figure 3 falls on the dots of value 2. Then here in Figure 8, there will be the formation of the second trivial red diagonal $x_{d=n} = 2y + 2$ of the trivial divisors $d = n$ on the following dots also of value 2 in MHL.

The two red trivial diagonals $x_{d=1} = y + 2$ and $x_{d=n} = 2y + 2$ delimit the lower trivial divisors $d = 1$ and highest trivial divisors $d = n$. They set the sizes (or ranges) for all the divisors d of integers n .

4.1 The ranges of the d divisors

For each integer n , the diagonals hypotenuse lines with slope -1 : n have the smallest possible slope. This happens for $d = n$ and $h = 1$. Divisors $d = n$ produce the red diagonal $x = 2y + 2$.

The maximum slope for each n is at slope $-n$: $n - 45^\circ$ for $d = 1$ and $h = n$. The formation of the red diagonal $x = y + 2$ of the divisors $d = 1$

If the formation of the red diagonal $x = y + 2$ of the divisors $d = 1$, for any n in the Modular Hyperbolic Lattice in Figure 3 falls on the dots of value 2, so now in Figure 4 there will be the formation of the red diagonal $x = 2y + 2$ of the divisors $d = n$ also on the dots of value 2.

The two red diagonals $x = y + 2$ and $x = 2y + 2$ delimit the minimum $d = 1$ and maximum $d = n$ sizes (range) for the divisors d .

Figure 9. C002264 The TSP two red diagonals $x = y + 2$ and $x = 2y + 2$ delimit the minimum $d_1 = 1$ and maximum $d_2 = n$ sizes (range) for the divisors d , respectively.

The red lines cover the minimum divisors $d_1 = 1$ at diagonal $x = y + 2$ and the maximum divisors $d_2 = n$ at diagonal $x = 2y + 2$ of all integers n . The two red diagonals delimit the widest possible range of the size of $\Delta d = d_2 - d_1$.

Thus, while all composite numbers have the largest Δd as delimited by the two red diagonals, which allow being $\Delta d_{\max} = n - 1$, only prime numbers have the smallest $\Delta d_{\min} = \Delta d_{\max} = \text{prime} - 1$ delimited by them. This is because all prime numbers have only one size for Δd .

Unlike prime and composite numbers, the number 1 has only size $\Delta d = 0$. This is because number 1 is a square number. All other squares will have $\Delta d_{\min} = 0$. for its maximum and minimum d.

The green lines fall on the minimum and maximum divisors of the integers n and that are not 1 or n itself. It is these green lines that delimit the range of the proper divisors $d \neq 1$ for each integer n .

5 The non-trivial divisors

As we will see below, the definition and formation of TSP is made with the divisors that are not trivial.

5.1 The hypotenuse lines of integers multiples of non-trivial divisor $d = 2$

From Figure 4, starting from hypotenuse line $x = -2y + \text{oblong} = -2y + (2^2 + 2) = -2y + 6$, then the hypotenuse lines multiples of 2 are:

Figure 10. C002257 The TSP multiples of 2 are the hypotenuse lines in the form of $x = -2y + (2^2 + 2)h$.

Here, for any n Integer we will set:

$$d = 2$$

$$\alpha = 1:2$$

$$Y = \frac{X}{d} = \frac{X}{2}$$

For each $1 \leq h = \text{Integer} < \infty$, we have:

$$n = hd = 2h$$

So, the points $D(n, n)$ over the diagonal 45° will be $D(2h, 2h)$ with the value $n = 2h$.

Each hypotenuse line will cross Y-axis at the point:

$$Y = (0, n + h) = (0, 2h + h) = (0, 3h)$$

Each hypotenuse line will cross X-axis at the point:

$$X = (n + m, 0) = (hd + hd^2, 0) = ((2^2 + 2)h, 0) = (6h, 0)$$

The equations of the hypotenuses passing through the points $D(n, n)$ when n is a multiple of 2 are:

$$\alpha = \frac{y - y_0}{x - x_0}$$

$$x - x_0 = \frac{y - y_0}{\alpha}$$

$$x - (2^2 + 2)h = \left(\frac{y - 0}{-\frac{1}{2}} \right)$$

$$x = -2y + (2^2 + 2)h = -2y + 6h$$

5.2 The hypotenuse lines of integers multiples of non-trivial divisor $d = 3$

From Figure 4, starting from hypotenuse line $x = -3y + oblong = -3y + (3^2 + 3) = -3y + 12$, then the hypotenuse lines multiples of 3 are:

Figure 11. C002258 The TSP multiples of 3 are the hypotenuse lines in the form of $x = -3y + (3^2 + 3)h$.

Here, for any n Integer we will set:

$$d = 3$$

$$\alpha = 1:3$$

$$Y = \frac{X}{d} = \frac{X}{3}$$

For each $1 \leq h = \text{Integer} \leq \infty$, we have:

$$n = hd = 3h$$

So, the points $D(n, n)$ over the diagonal 45° will be $D(3h, 3h)$ with the value $n = 3h$.

Each hypotenuse line will cross Y-axis at the point:

$$Y = (0, n + h) = (0, 3h + h) = (0, 4h)$$

Each hypotenuse line will cross X-axis at the point:

$$X = (n + m, 0) = (hd + hd^2, 0) = ((3^2 + 3)h, 0)$$

The equations of the hypotenuses passing through the points $D(n, n)$ when n is a multiple of 3 are:

$$\alpha = \frac{y - y_0}{x - x_0}$$

$$x - x_0 = \frac{y - y_0}{\alpha}$$

$$x - (3^2 + 3)h = \frac{y - 0}{-\frac{1}{3}}$$

$$x = -3y + (3^2 + 3)h$$

5.3 The hypotenuse lines of integers multiples of non-trivial divisor $d = 4$

From Figure 4, starting from hypotenuse line $x = -4y + oblong = -4y + (4^2 + 4) = -4y + 20$, then the hypotenuse lines multiples of 4 are:

Figure 12. C002259 The multiples of 4 are the hypotenuse lines in the form of $x = -4y + (4^2 + 4)h$.

Here, for any n Integer we will set:

$$d = 4$$

$$\alpha = 1:4$$

$$Y = \frac{X}{d} = \frac{X}{4}$$

For each $1 \leq h = \text{Integer} \leq \infty$, we have:

$$n = hd = 4h$$

So, the points $D(n, n)$ over the diagonal 45° will be $D(4h, 4h)$ with the value $n = 4h$.

Each hypotenuse line will cross Y-axis at the point:

$$Y = (0, n + h) = (0, 4h + h) = (0, 5h)$$

Each hypotenuse line will cross X-axis at the point:

$$X = (n + m, 0) = (hd + hd^2, 0) = ((4^2 + 4)h, 0)$$

The equations of the hypotenuses passing through the points $D(n, n)$ when n is a multiple of 4 are:

$$\alpha = \frac{y - y_0}{x - x_0}$$

$$x - x_0 = \frac{y - y_0}{\alpha}$$

$$x - (4^2 + 4)h = \frac{y - 0}{-\frac{1}{4}}$$

$$x = -4y + (4^2 + 4)h$$

5.4 The hypotenuse lines of integers multiples of non-trivial divisor $d = 5$

From Figure 4, starting from hypotenuse line $x = -5y + oblong = -5y + (5^2 + 5) = -5y + 30$, then the hypotenuse lines multiples of 5 are:

Figure 13. C002260 The TSP multiples of 5 are the hypotenuse lines in the form of $x = -5y + (5^2 + 5)h$.

Here, for any n Integer we will set:

$$d = 5$$

$$\alpha = 1:5$$

$$Y = \frac{X}{d} = \frac{X}{5}$$

For each $1 \leq h = \text{Integer} \leq \infty$, we have:

$$n = hd = 5h$$

So, the points $D(n, n)$ over the diagonal 45° will be $D(5h, 5h)$ with the value $n = 5h$.

Each hypotenuse line will cross Y-axis at the point:

$$Y = (0, n + h) = (0, 5h + h) = (0, 6h)$$

Each hypotenuse line will cross X-axis at the point:

$$X = (n + m, 0) = (hd + hd^2, 0) = ((5^2 + 5)h, 0)$$

The equations of the hypotenuses passing through the points $D(n, n)$ when n is a multiple of 5 are:

$$\alpha = \frac{y - y_0}{x - x_0}$$

$$x - x_0 = \frac{y - y_0}{\alpha}$$

$$x - (5^2 + 5)h = \frac{y - 0}{-\frac{1}{5}}$$

$$x = -5y + (5^2 + 5)h$$

5.5 All the hypotenuse lines of all multiples

For any n Integer, we set non-trivial divisor d :

$$1 < d < n$$

$$\alpha = 1:d$$

$$Y = \frac{X}{d}$$

For each $1 \leq h = \text{Integer} \leq \infty$, we have:

$$n = hd$$

So, the points $D(n, n)$ over the diagonal 45° will be $D(hd, hd)$ with the value $n = hd$.

Each hypotenuse line will cross Y-axis at the point:

$$Y = (0, n + h) = (0, hd + h) = (0, h(d + 1))$$

Each hypotenuse line will cross X-axis at the point:

$$X = (n + m, 0) = (hd + hd^2, 0) = (h(d^2 + d), 0) = (h(\text{oblong}), 0)$$

The general equations of the hypotenuses passing through the points $D(n, n)$ when n is a multiple of divisor d are:

$$\alpha = \frac{y - y_0}{x - x_0}$$

$$x - x_0 = \frac{y - y_0}{\alpha}$$

$$x - h(d^2 + d) = \frac{y - 0}{-\frac{1}{d}}$$

$$x = -dy + h(d^2 + d)$$

6 The triangular sieve of prime numbers

As a result, we get the Triangular Sieve of Primes over the yellow 45° diagonal $x = y$.

Figure 14. [C000247](#) C002261 The TSP with all the hypotenuse lines for non-trivial divisors $1 < d < n$.

To see a larger picture, the link is [C000247](#).

Composite numbers are the integers over the 45° diagonal $x = y$ that have at least one hypotenuse line for non-trivial divisors (in maroon) covering them.

Only square numbers have an odd number of hypotenuse lines for non-trivial divisors (in maroon) covering them.

Only the squares of the prime numbers have only one hypotenuse line for non-trivial divisors (in maroon) covering it. No maroon triangle.

The prime numbers have no hypotenuse lines for non-trivial divisors (in maroon) covering them.

TSP shows where the positive composite numbers are over the yellow 45° diagonal.

TSP one does not differentiate 1 from prime numbers. Number 1 is a prime number.

Thus, just in the interval for non-trivial divisors $1 < d < n$, for every integer n , our TSP can detect all positive composite numbers.

All Integers over the yellow 45° diagonal obey following the rules:

- The composite number 0 has infinitely many maroon lines.
- All other composite numbers <https://oeis.org/A002808> have a finite number of maroon lines crossing it.
- The prime numbers <https://oeis.org/A008578> have no maroon lines.
- The square numbers <http://oeis.org/A000290> always have an odd number of maroon lines.
- The squares of the prime numbers <https://oeis.org/A001248> always have only one maroon line.
- The composites, which are not square numbers <https://oeis.org/A089229>, always have an even number of maroon lines covering them.

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Conflicts of Interest

The author declare no conflicts of interest.

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